

A STUDY OF RAVNAQ'S LIFE AND WORK

Shadiyeva Dilafroz Abduxalil kizi

TSUULL faculty of philology 4th year

dilijan.shad@gmail.com

+998944125262

Abstract: The article provides information about the research on the study of Pahlavonquli Ravnaq from Khorezm, who lived and created in the second half of the 18th century. At the same time, opinions were noted that the poet's literary heritage should first be realized in the aspect of source studies and textual studies.

Keyword: divan, manuscript, Ravnaq, ghazal, muhammas, poet, ta'rix.

In the history of the Great Khorezm state, many khans sat on the throne. By the 18th century, this process accelerated. During this period, several khans ruled in Khorezm: Shahgazi Khan (1765-1767), Muhammad Amin Inaq (1770-1790), Avazbi Inaq (1782-1804), Eltuzar Khan (1804-1806), Muhammad Rahim Khan I (1806-1825). In this dangerous time, along with highly talented poets such as Andalib, Muhammad Hoxor, Roqim, Nishoti, Pahlavanquli Ravnaq also lived and worked in Khorezm [1, 2010, 520].

Information about Pahlavanquli Ravnaq is first found in Munis and Ogahi's historical work "Firdavs ul-Iqbal" [1, 2010, 106-155]. In this work, Munis focused on Pahlavi Ravnaq in two places. First, a fragment of the history written by Ravnaq dedicated to Shah Temurghazi is given: *"Hamul kun Temurg'ozixon Muhammadamin mehtarning taqviyati bila Muhammadamin bek bila Muhammad inoqg'a ul ikki amiri maqtulning mansablarin shafqat qildi. Va amiri kabir Muhammadamin inoqning ibtidoiyi davlati ul kundindur. Va Bichan yili Muhammadamin mehtar bila xon o'rtasida ba'zi umuri mulkiy jihatdin vahshat tushdi. Bu sababdin aning buyruqi bila Safar dasturxonchi va Abdusattorboy xonni o'ldurdilar. Aning favtig'a mavlono Pahlavonquli Ravnaq ta'rix aytibdurkim.*

Ta'rix:

Shah Temurg'ozijahondinborg'ach,

Bo'ldi ta'rix anga "xurshidi janob" [1, 2010, 106-155].

V. Abdullayev in his "History of Uzbek Literature" chronology in 1964, based on the "Ta'rix" given in this work of Munis, it is assumed that Pahlavonquli Ravnaq "was born in 1730 and died at the end of the 18th century" [2, 1966, 101-161]. In order to confirm this opinion, he turns the sentence "Khurshedi Janob" in "Ta'rix" to the abjad calculation and shows that it must be 1176 Hijri, 1763-64 AD.

When the letters in the sentence "Khurshedi Janab" in this "Ta'rix" are re-checked by abjad calculation (X - 600, u - 6, r - 200, sh -300, i - 10, d - 4, j - 3, n - 50, a - 1, b - 2) originated in 1176 Hijri. When we converted it to AD year (1176-(1176:33)+622=) it turned out to be 1762.

In the "History of Uzbek Literature" chronology, it was found that the year of writing of the poet's "Ta'rix" was wrongly stated by one or two years AD [3, 1964, 174-175].

In this chronology, it is said that the poet's manuscript "Devoni Ravnaq" is kept at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences №291-II, and it was copied by the secretary Muhammad Yusuf. However, this manuscript does not provide information about the poet's poetic genre. In addition, it is said that the manuscript "Bayozi mutafarriqa" compiled during the reign of Muhammad Rahim II in Kheva also contains poems of the Bayoz poet [3, 1964, 174-175]. This resource is currently stored in the main fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies under inventory number #6960.

In 1785, the daughter of Muhammad Amin Mehtar died. On this occasion, his friend Pahlavanquli Ravnak wrote a lament. On the marble stone above the door of the mausoleum placed by Muhammad Amin Mehtar at the entrance to the Pahlavon Muhammad shrine in Khiva (on the right side) is the inscription "Yo Rab, ul hur

yerin ravzayi rizvon etgil, Nozanin ruhini masti mayi g'ufyon etgil" , verses are said to have been copied. [3, 1964, 174-175; 4, 2006, 92-95].

V. Abdullayev in his "History of Uzbek Literature" chronicles in 1978, the birth and death of the poet according to the content of his eventful ghazal: "Ravnaq was ill and was forgotten by his friends, Minister Matniyoz came and learned about the poet's condition... Matniyoz was the head of Muhammad Niyozbek, who participated in Eltuzar's attack on Karakalpak in 1803-1804 and returned with a lot of gold and property [5, 1960, 93-95] . So, the poet was alive in the early years of the 19th century [3, 1964, 174-218]. Based on this, it was concluded that the poet "lived and in the years 1725-1805".

In another place of the work "Firdavs ul-Iqbal", there is information about the poet entering into a "discussion" with Nishoti. This case is recorded as follows: "... *ul chog 'da tarokima tavoyifidin taka xalqi navkarlik tariqasi bila kelib, Yangiariq va Ostona hududida mutamakkin erdilar. Alar sharorati zotiy va jaholati jibilliy harakatidinkim, ul tavoyifidin badiynat maxsusidur, ba'zi umuri noshoyista tamhidig'a iqdom ko'rguzub, balki, farmoni vojib al-iz'ondin goho bo'yun to'lg'ar edilar. Andoqkim, safari mazkurda Fozilbekning mulozimatidin taxalluf joyiz tuttilar Muhammadamin inoq bu jihatdin alarni Fozil bek kelgandin so'ng yurtidin chiqadi. Bir necha kundin so'ng Bobo bekkim, moddayi fasod va xamirmoyayi inoq erdi, takadin Zamonbek va solurdin Otdiron Bahodirni yuz kishi bila o'z inisi Abdulrahmon bekning mulozimatida Jonmurod inoqg'a madad uchun yubordi. Mavlono Pahlavonquli Ravnaq bu bobda taarruz (tegajoqlik) yuzidin bu baytni aytib yubordi. Bayt:*

Qo'rqitma mani Sorito-yu, Butu Buroqingdin,

K...¹g'a g'am Otdironu Angg'oqingdin.

¹K... - in which masculinity is implied. Translated from the Arabic script, authors of the introduction and comments: Shodmon Vahidov, Ismail Bekchanov and Ne'matjon Polvanov).

Ma'lum bo'lsunkim "Angg'iloq" din iborat Zamonbekdur. Va qozi Muhammadniyoz Nishotiykim, Jonmurod inoqning anis va jalisi erdi, bu baytni aning javobida aytib yubordi. Bayt:

Qo'rqutma mani Boynazaru Bekpo'lotingdin,

K...g'a ne g'am turkmonu chovduru sholotingdin.

Va Muhammadamin inoq bu xabarni eshitib, hazmu ehtiyot jonibin mar'i tutub, Toji biy qiyotni ikki yuz kishi bila Xo'jaylining muhofazatig'a nomzad qildi..." [1, 2010, 155-156]. Olmoskhan Abdurahmanova in her PhD research paper "Textual Analysis of Nishoti's Discussions" says that "*Pahlavanquli Ravnaq and Muhammad Niyoz Nishoti lived at the same time and both poets had a mutual "shokh way" of communication*" [7, 2021, 36]. This information is found in Muhammad Yusuf Bayani's work "Tawarihi Khorezm". And V. Abdullayev mentions that "*...Muhammad Yusuf Bayani's work "Shajarayi Khorazmshahi" also contains this comic piece...*" [5, #7421; 3, 1964, 174-175].

In 1966, V. Zohidov gave information about the life and work of Pahlavanquli Ravnaq in the "Uzbek literature" chronology. It is rightly emphasized that "*Ravnaq's life and work have not been fully studied*" [2, 1966, 161-200]. It is said that the poet was created in the Persian-Tajik and Turkish languages. This is given by the example of the poet's poems copied to a manuscript cabinet kept №922 in Republic Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences. However, this manuscript indicates that the scribe who copied the divan is not "*Muhammad Yaqub ibn Usta Qurbanniyaz Khorezmi divan*" but "*Muhammad Yusuf*".

In this the poet's 24 ghazals, 1 mustazad, 2 Navoi ghazals, 1 Fuzuli ghazal, and 1 *qasida* are attached [1, №922, 1-80]. First, we have given the first verses of the poet's published **ghazals** below: "*Surtub yuzumi tun kecha dildor eshigida...*" (10 couplet), "*Na bir qosidki yetkirsal salomim jona jonimg'a...*" (7 couplet), "*Bu kun bir dilraboni ko'rdimki sochi ol yangog' uzra...*" (7 couplet), "*Yondim sevarim, xoh inon, xoh inonma...*" (11 couplet), "*Ey malak siymoki, olam xalqidur hayron*

sango...” (7 couplet) , “*Jilva qilib yuz ia ul sanami komyob...*” (11 couplet), “*Xaramdin chiqti ul sarvi gulandonim xirom aylab...*” (9 couplet), “*Ne niholi umr erur sarvi xiromoningcha xo 'b...*” (7 couplet), “*Va 'dayi vasl berib aylamak ehmol nedur...*” (9 couplet), “*Ul parivashki quyoshdek guli ruxsorasi bor...*” (7 couplet), “*Inoyat chog 'i do 'st istig 'noi nozin ko 'r...*” (7 couplet), “*Xo 'blar jahonda sendek sohibjamol emastur...*” (9 couplet), “*Dunyoiki dunki kimga dey oing vafosi bor...*” (7 couplet), “*Ne ishvau, ne nozu karashma, ne adodur...*” (9 couplet), “*Ne jo 'rayi zamonada bor erkan e 'tibor...*” (7 couplet), “*Bu ne tole ' edikim qilmadi imdod hanuz...*” (9 couplet), “*Chiqsa noz aylab haramdin sho 'xi siyminsiq qiz...*” (10 couplet), “*Ohkim, tushgali bu zoli falakka ishimiz...*” (11 couplet), “*Keldingu ketding ko 'rimay, ey par paykar sanam...*” (7 couplet), “*Evrulay boshiga, zebo sanamim, dildorim...*” (10 couplet), “*Xush kelibsan buyon, parizodim...*” (13 couplet), “*Ul o 'tlug ' chehrakim olamg 'a o 't solmish jamolidin...*” (8 couplet), “*Ayladi yor jahondin safar, afsus – afsus...*” (13 couplet), “*Ne oy yuzlik, shaker guftorlig ' zebo sanamdur bu...*”(11 couplet). **The first misra of mustazod:** “*Mastona chiqib qatlima bodom qabog 'i, beboki sitamgar...*” (14 band), **The taxmises by Ravnaq to Navai and Fuzuli's ghazals:** “*Garchi a 'jozi Masiho ma 'li durposhidadur...*” (5 band), “*Ne sitam gar yetsa sendin, jonajonim sen mening...*” (5 band), “*Xodisoti dahri dundin ko 'nglinga g 'am bo 'lmasun...*” (5 band). **Qasida:** “*Buncha javring degil, ey charxi sitamkor, nedur...*” (42 bayt).

V. Abdullayev also wrote down valuable information about the life and activities of Pahlavonquli Ravnaq in his 1978 chronology [6, 1978, 304]. There are records of many poets who wrote under the pseudonym "Ravnaq" before the time of Pahlavanquli Ravnaq. In this, Pahlavanquli Ravnaq poems are divided into such groups as "*Genre features of Ravnaq lyrics*", "*Thematic framework and ideological motives of Ravnaq lyrics*", "*Poetic features of Ravnaq lyrics*", and the scope of the topic is clarified. In addition, it is said that one manuscript of Pahlavanquli Ravnaq, that is, a source kept №922 in the UzR Academy of Sciences, has arrived. It is said

that this divan includes 258 ghazals (4168 lines), one mustazadi (14 lines), 22 muhammas (745) and 5 odes (324 lines), totaling 286 lyrical works of 5251 lines. But it does not provide information about the scribe who copied this manuscript. This information is also found in the textbook "History of Uzbek Literature" prepared by Rahmonkul Orzibekov in 2006 [4, 2006, 92-95].

When we examined this manuscript divan, it is clear that **253** ghazals, 1 mustazad, **20** (13 of which were written by **Navoi**, 3 by **Fuzuli**, 4 by **his own ghazal**) and **6** qasidas were copied. It can be seen that V. Abdullayev gave 5 ghazals of the poet, and 2 more than the number of ghazals. It turned out that he counted less than one **poem** (Full information about this is given in the chapter "*Scientific description of the manuscripts of the Poet's Office*") [1, №922].

V. Abdullayev's "Selection" was published in 1982 under the title "Literary-Critical Articles". In his article "Poets of Muhammadoti Mutafarriqa" in the book "Poets - Followers of Navoi", Pahlavonquli admires the ghazals of Ravnaq, Nishoti, Rakim, Andalib, Sarvar, Volahi, Vafai, Kiromi, Ohi, Mazun, Jinoi, Rifatii's ghazals Lutfi, Jami, Navoi, Fuzuli Shaidai. gives information about the connection [9, 1982, 146-153]. He especially highly appreciates Ravnaq, Nishoti, and Kiromi's works related to Navoi's ghazals. This can be seen in: *Alisher Navoi's ghazals ending with rhymes or radifs such as "barot - zakat", "manzari - pari", "tutubmen - unutibmen", "deyin", "yana", "mening", "sanchar" were woven by Pahlavanquli Ravnaq, the muhammas which are mentioned in "Muhammadoti mutafarriqa" are really mature and praiseworthy muhammas. Example:*

Tokay mani, ey gardun, g'am xastasi qilgaysen,

Hijron qilichin tortib, bag'rim necha tilgaysen,

Ey baxt, qachon bir kun holim so'ra kelgaysen,

Sanchilgan ajal xori ishq uchrasa bilgaysen,

Kim jong'a balo neshin hajr o'zgacharoq sanchar... " [9, 1982, 146-153].

In Ayyomi's "Fire-Flashing Lines" it is mentioned that talented poets such as Andalib, Roqim, Pahlavonquli Ravnaq, Muhammad Khoksor lived in Khorezm in the 17th - 18th centuries. In this, there are notes about the fact that Orientalists and literary scholars often had a one-sided opinion about the cultural and literary environment of Khorezm in the 17th century. Yunus Yusupov denies the opinion of Academician V.V. Barthold that in the 17th century there was only Abulgozi, and in the 18th century "it was a period of silence in literature"[10, 1927, 101; 11, 1983, 15-16]. During this period, a number of events related to the political game (struggle for the throne) and the way of life of the common people took place. But in Khorezm, several beautiful works of Andalib, such as "Yusuf and Zulayho", "Zainularab", "Layli and Majnun", Nishatiy's "Husnu Dil", "Birds' Discussion", Munis's "Munis ul Ushshaq", "Firdavs ul-Iqbal" were published in the world. [7, 2021, 36; 3, 1964, 174-175]. At the same time, Pahlavanquli Ravnak, another poet with unique talent, also lived in this period. The poet created in the genres of masnavi, rubai, murabba mukhammas, qasida, ta'rix, mustazad. It is clearly visible that he was influenced by the works of Navoi and Fuzuli and wrote a number of naziras and mukhammas[1, №922]. At the same time, Roqim, a contemporary of the poet, Shermuhammad Munis, who lived at the end of the 18th and the beginning of the 19th century, and the poets of the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century: Mirza, Mutrib, Tabibi and several other poets, were influenced by the works of Ravnaq of Pahlavi. This confirms that the above opinions of Yunus Yusupov are correct [№7054; №2679/II, 280; №L-8731]. It is clear from the researches that the poet's poems have not been published in full. It is necessary to study the poems of Pahlavanquli Ravnak from the point of view of textual studies and source studies. When studying the work of the poet, first of all, it is necessary to collect his poems copied into manuscript sources. At the same time, it is necessary to carry out a scientific monographic description of all the manuscripts from which the poet's poems were copied, and to show the textual-comparative differences of the published poems.

After that, it is important to prepare the poet's manuscript for publication. This creates a basis for studying the artistry of the poet's poems. The following conclusions can be drawn from the studies of the poet's life and work:

- initially, information about the poet's biography was given in Munis's work "Firdavs ul-Iqbal" (until 1813). After that, it was found that the historical work (Muhammad Yusuf Bayani's "Shajarayi Khorazmshahi") written in the second half of the 19th century contains certain information about the poet's work. Before the years of independence, the life and work of Pahlavonquli Ravnaq was studied by V. Zohidov, V. Abdullayev, Ayyomi. In 1967, O. Rasulova's candidacy work entitled "*Poet Pahlavonquli Ravnaq*" was carried out (However, this research work has not been found yet). After independence, in 2006, R. Orzubekov provided information on the study of the poet's work and the artistry of his works in the "History of Uzbek Literature" textbook.

- secondly, in "Firdavs ul-Iqbal" of Munis, Ravnaq's "History" dedicated to the death of Temurghazi Khan is given. V. Abdullayev indicated the year of writing of this "History" as 1763-1764. However, when we checked it again, it became clear that "History" was written in 1762, not 1763-1764.

Thirdly, 24 ghazals, 3 muhammas, and 1 ode of Pahlavanquli Ravnaq have been published to date. And some (parts of matla' and makta') ghazals and important ones are given in christomatiies. It can be seen that the content, scope and artistry of the poet's works have not been fully studied. For this, in the study of Ravnaq's work, his literary heritage in manuscripts should first be studied from the point of view of textual studies and source studies.

References:

1. Munis va Ogahiy. (2010) Firdavs ul-iqbol. – Toshkent, Yangi asr avlodi nashriyoti. –B. 520.
2. O‘zbek adabiyoti. (1966) Xrestomatiya. IV tom. I kitob (Nashrga tayyorlovchi V.Zohidov). – Toshkent, Badiiy adabiyot nashriyoti. – B. 101-161.

3. O‘zbek adabiyoti tarixi (XVII – XIX (I yarmi) asrlar). (2006) (Nashrga tayyorlovchi Rahmonqul Orzibekov). – Toshkent, O‘zbekiston Yozuvchilar uyushmasi Adabiyot jamg ‘armasi nashriyoti. – B. 92-95.
4. V.Abdullayev. (1982) Saylanma. Adabiy-tanqidiy maqolalar. – Toshkent, G‘afur G‘ulom nomidagi Adabiyot va san’at nashriyoti. – B. 146-153.
5. Ayyomiy. (1983) O‘t chaqnagan satrlar. – Toshkent, – B. 15-16.
6. Мадиримова, С. М. (2018). О СЮЖЕТЕ ПОЭМЫ «АШИК ГАРИБ И ШАХСАНАМ». *Редакционная коллегия*, 109.
7. Madirimova, S. (2019). Mutrib Xonaxarob asarlari qo ‘lyozmalarining ilmiy tavsifi. *Oltin bitiglar–Golden Scripts*, 3(3).
8. Jabbarov, N. (2010). What is education. *Tashkent. Ma’naviyat*.
9. Jabborov, N. (2023). ALISHER NAVOIY IJODINING ISLOMIY-MA’RIFIY ASOSLARI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(Conference Proceedings 1), 19-30.
10. Mirzakarimovna, R. D. (2022). Literary-aesthetic thinking-a factor of renewal of poetic image in tavallo's work. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(5), 195-199.